

Migration of a Left Tunneled Jugular Catheter in The Mediastinum

M Raouti^{1*}, F Lamouime¹, M Tachaouine¹, H Naouli^{2,3}, A Bougheroum^{2,3}, M Lakranbi^{1,2}, Y Ouadnoui^{1,2}, M Smahi^{1,2}

¹Department of Thoracic Surgery University Hospital FES

²Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University Faculty of Medicine (Fes)

³Department of Vascular Surgery University Hospital FES

Citation: M Raouti, F Lamouime, M Tachaouine, H Naouli, A Bougheroum, M Lakranbi, et al. Migration of a Left Tunneled Jugular Catheter in The Mediastinum. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(4):1-2.

Received Date: 21 April, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 23 April, 2024; **Published Date:** 25 April, 2024

***Corresponding author:** M Raouti, Department of Thoracic Surgery University Hospital FES

Copyright: © M Raouti, Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

CLINICAL IMAGE

55 years old patient with chronic haemodialysis 3 times a week, presenting with a failed maturation in his left radial arteriovenous fistula, coupled with right fistula stenosis and very significant swelling of the upper limb, as well as stenosis of the right brachiocephalic trunk; having benefitted from 4 angioplasties all doomed to failure. Patient was admitted to the nephrology department for the placement of a left tunneled jugular catheter, which ended up migrating to the mediastinum. A CT angiography was performed, revealing an extravasation of the venous contrast medium from the left brachiocephalic venous trunk coming opposite the catheter of which the distal tip is at the anterior mediastinum (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Thoracic CT angiography showing the catheter at the mediastinum

The patient underwent a median sternotomy. Surgical exploration found the catheter piercing the posterior wall of the brachiocephalic venous trunk and the thymus (Figure 2), creating a haematoma on its path to the pericardium (Figure 3).

Figure 2 : A : Operating view showing a catheter that pierces the thymus and reaches the pericardium
B: Catheter piercing the posterior wall of the left brachiocephalic venous trunk.

Figure 3: Operating view showing a haematoma on the catheter path